

Synthesis of Substituted 3-Arylaminomethyl-7-chloro-4-(3H)-quinazolinones

RAJENDRA S. VARMA and ANIL K. AGNIHOTRI

Department of Chemistry, Lucknow University, Lucknow-226 907

Manuscript received 15 September 1977, revised 10 July 1978, accepted 22 August 1978

Some substituted 3-arylaminomethyl 7-chloro-4-(3H)-quinazolinones have been synthesised under the conditions of the Mannich reaction.

A MIDES and imides such as salicylamide¹, succinimide^{2,3}, phthalimide⁴⁻⁶ and 4-nitrophthalimide⁷ having an active hydrogen atom on nitrogen have been reported to undergo Mannich condensations furnishing N-alkamine derivatives in good yields. 7-Chloro-4(3H)-quinazolinone (I) may be regarded as a cyclic amide whose hydrogen attached to N-3 should be sufficiently active due to electron withdrawing character of chlorine atom and carbonyl group to participate in the Mannich reaction. In view of this and diverse pharmacological behaviour of quinazolinones^{8,9} it was therefore considered of interest to utilise I for the synthesis of N-3-alkamine derivatives. The present communication deals with the preparation of some 3-arylamino-methyl-4(3H)-quinazolinones (II) by Mannich condensation.

2-Amino-4-chlorobenzoic acid was fused with formamide to yield I which on treatment with formalin and aromatic primary amines in equimolar proportions furnished II, as characterised by elemental analysis and spectral (i. r. and n. m. r.) data.

It has already been established¹⁰ that the Mannich reaction on 4-(3H)-quinazolinone takes

place at N-3 and not at N-1 by means of U.V. data of II(R=H) which was in agreement with the reported results¹⁰.

Representative compounds when tested against *Plasmodium berghei berghei* N strain (=Keyberg 173) did not show any significant activity.

R = H, Me, Cl, Br, F, OMe, OEt, CO₂H, CO₂Me, CO₂Et, CO₂Pr, Ph.

TABLE - SUBSTITUTED 3-ARYLAMINOMETHYL-7-CHLORO-4(3H)-QUINAZOLINONES(II)

Sl. No.	R	M. P. °C	% Yield	Mol. formula*
1.	H	185	60	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ ClN ₂ O
2.	4-Me	177	50	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ ClN ₂ O
3.	3-Me	165-66	50	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ ClN ₂ O
4.	4-OMe	155	50	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ ClN ₂ O ₂
5.	2-OEt	135	60	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ ClN ₂ O ₂
6.	4-OEt	175	55	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ ClN ₂ O ₂
7.	2-Ph	145	50	C ₂₁ H ₁₆ ClN ₂ O
8.	4-Ph	142	50	C ₂₁ H ₁₆ ClN ₂ O
9.	2-CO ₂ H	215	45	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ ClN ₂ O ₃
10.	3-CO ₂ H	205	40	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ ClN ₂ O ₃
11.	4-CO ₂ H	220	40	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ ClN ₂ O ₃
12. ^a	3-CO ₂ Me	174-75	50	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ ClN ₂ O ₂
13.	4-CO ₂ Me	182	45	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ ClN ₂ O ₂
14. ^b	4-CO ₂ Et	165	55	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ ClN ₂ O ₂
15.	4-CO ₂ Pr	165	60	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ ClN ₂ O ₂
16.	4-Br	200-01	55	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ BrClN ₂ O
17.	3-Cl	215	50	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ Cl ₂ N ₂ O
18. ^a	4-Cl	208	60	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ Cl ₂ N ₂ O
19.	4-F	165-67	40	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ ClFN ₂ O

*Satisfactory nitrogen analyses were obtained for all the compounds. Compounds 1, 4, 6, 11, 15, 16 and 17 were recrystallized from ethyl acetate (since they hydrolysed in ethanol) others were recrystallized from ethanol.

a. I.R. 3270 (NH), 1690 (ester), 1675 (C=O, ring) cm⁻¹ for compound 12 and 3270 (NH), 1678 (C=O) cm⁻¹ for compound 18.

b. N.M.R. (δ ppm) : 1.23t(Me), 4.08-4.70 m(N-CH₂N, NH, OCH₂) 6.7-8.2m(Ar-H).

Experimental

Melting points were taken in open capillaries in sulfuric acid bath and are uncorrected. Infrared spectra were recorded in a Perkin-Elmer 177 instrument in KBr and n. m. r. spectrum was recorded in CDCl_3 -DMSO- d_6 in an Varian A-60 spectrometer.

7-Chloro-4 (3H)-quinazolinone(I) was prepared according to known procedure.^{11,12}

3-Arylaminomethyl-7-chloro-4(3H)-quinazolinones(II)

A mixture of I (1.80 g., 0.01 mole), formalin (1.5 ml) and an appropriate aromatic primary amine (0.01 mole) were taken in 25 ml of ethanol. The reaction mixture was heated on a waterbath with stirring for 10 min. It was allowed to stand at room temperature overnight. The solid mass thus deposited was filtered and recrystallised from a suitable solvent. The compounds prepared are recorded in the Table.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to the Head of the Chemistry Department for providing facilities. Thanks are due to CSIR, New Delhi for financial assistant (JRF to AKA) and to the Director, C. D. R. I., Lucknow for elemental analyses and spectral

data. Thanks are also due to Dr. W. Peters, Liverpool School of Tropical Medicine, U. K. for antimalarial screening.

References

1. R. S. VARMA, *Curr. Sci.*, 1972, 41, 416.
2. J. R. FELDMAN and E. C. WAGNER. *J. Org. Chem.*, 1942, 7, 31.
3. H. HELLMANN, I. LOSCHMANN and F. LINGENS, *Ber.*, 1954, 87, 1784, 1690.
4. W. I. WEAVER, J. K. SIMONS and W. E. BALDWIN. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1944, 66, 222.
5. M. B. MOORE and R. T. RAPELA, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1946, 68, 1657.
6. R. O. ATKINSON, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 1329.
7. R. S. VARMA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1973, 50, 495.
8. A. H. AMIN, D.R. MEHTA and S.S. SAMARTH in "Progress in Drug Research" (Ed.) E. JUCKER, Birkhauser Verlag, Basel, 1970, Vol. 14, p. 218.
9. W. L. F. ARMAREGO in "Advances in Heterocyclic Chemistry" (Ed.) A. R. KATRITZKY, Academic Press, New York, 1963, Vol. 1, p. 304.
10. B. R. BAKER, M. V. QUERRY, A. F. KADISH and J. H. WILLIAMS, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1952, 17, 35.
11. M. M. ENDICOTT, E. WICK, M. L. MERCURY and M. L. SHERRILL, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1946, 68, 1299.
12. J. P. JOSEPH, F. J. McEVROY and J. H. WILLIAMS, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1952, 17, 141.